

ESTIMATING ECONOMICS-MAJORED STUDENTS' USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS FOR STUDYING ENGLISH THROUGH THE TECHNOLOGICAL ACCEPTANCE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The paper aims at using the numeric correlation among the TAM's components to explore, understand and estimate college students' use of information and communication technology (ICT) for learning English. The sample involved 320 freshmen of Economics at the University of Finance-Marketing (UFM), and they filled out a survey form electronically about three months after having experienced the use of ICT for studying English. The major findings show that the original research model consisting of five factors is transformed to the one with four because perceived usefulness and attitude to use are grouped via the exploratory factor analysis and renamed as behavioral attitude to use. The research also indicates that previous experiences with ICT principally influence students' perceived ease of use and their intention to use is determined by their behavioral attitude to use.

Key words: information and communication technology, technological tool, behavioral attitude, behavioral intention

1 INTRODUCTION

Blended learning is an educational model that has a face to face class or tutorial component combined with an online learning (Zanjani, F.V.M and Ramazani, M., 2012; Sen, 2011). This approach of teaching and learning is not new, and it has proven to be more effective than the face to face classroom or only online learning (Bogart, W V.D. and Wichadee, S., 2015).

Despite teacher resistance to the use of technology in education, blended learning has increased rapidly, driven by evidence of its advantages over either online or classroom teaching alone (L. M., Milne, J., Suddaby. G., & Higgins, A. , 2014). The teaching and learning of English are currently in the post-method era, where teachers focus much on classroom procedures with the aid of technological tools to maximize the students' learning outcome. Accordingly, traditional classrooms, typically equipped with chalk and blackboards as teaching aids are being replaced at a speedy rate by cyber-classrooms, where students have a much better chance to experience ICT tools while learning English (Zanjani, F.V.M and Ramazani, M., 2012). Although most higher education institutions (HEIs) in Vietnam claim to modernize their teaching and learning environment with the installation of ICT tools, the number of researches focusing on applying the TAM, which has long been believed to be a powerful tool to predict the acceptance of or

resistance to ICT use in learning foreign languages is quite few. Therefore, the TAM is surely an urgent need to help explore, understand and estimate college students' actual use of ICT for learning English.

2 Literature review

2.1 ICT tools

ICT tools, based on their application in education, have gone through several distinct stages of development. Before the boom of the Internet, audio-visual aids mostly consisting of tapes, radios, cassettes, CD players, overhead projectors, TVs, video tapes and records had been used to assist teaching and learning via conveying authentic materials to learners (Le, T ThanhHoa, 2016). Then, with the fast growth of websites around the year of 2000, Web 1.0 or the first generation web such as blogs, Wikipidia, or Google was widely used, and people could resort to this resource to search for necessary materials for their work. Since about 2004, Web 2.0 has been adopted by many as an interactive source where people can do more active jobs such as uploading, discussing or sharing information with other people on the Internet and Web 2.0 tools are popular in today's language classes (Ho, ThuyAn, 2016; Le, T ThanhHoa, 2016).

Dang (2013, as cited in Nguyen, XuanMinh, 2017) has classified ICT tools based on their functions in education. Ranging from electronic tools to digital ones and software applications, they serve various purposes such as location, retrieval, material creation, interaction and instruction support.

Table 1: Types of ICT tools for use in teaching

Tool category	Examples
Location and retrieval tools	Search engines: Google, Yahoo, Bing, Youtube, Teachertube, TV, Radio and the like
Material creation tools	Word processors, presentation software (Power Point, Prezzi), authoring programs (hot potatoes, task magic, and fun with texts), audio and video editing tools, e-lecture tools to merge movies into slides, make movies and mind maps, and the like
Interaction tools	Students' computers and smart phones connected with teachers' computer, Learning Management Systems or social networks
Teaching tools	PowerPoint or Keynote presentation Prezzi used with projectors

(Dang, 2013, as cited in Nguyen, Xuan Minh, 2017)

Concerning ICT tools, Puentedura (2006) also suggested the SAMR model to categorize them. The model, accordingly, is composed of four functions, including *substitution* (ICT as a direct tool substitute), *augmentation* (ICT as a direct tool substitute), *modification* (ICT as redesign of significant tasks), and *redefinition* (ICT as creation of new tasks). (Puentedura, 2006, as cited in

Nguyen, Xuan Minh, 2017, p347). In reality, these four functions are widely adopted to facilitate various educational tasks such as teaching, learning, testing and management.

Using ICT tools for teaching and learning English has been a trend, and there are several studies of the application of ITC tools to teach or learn English, for example the Flipped classroom model (Tran, TinNghi (a), 2017; Nguyen, S LanAnh & Le, ThiNgoc, 2017), using Web 2.0 tools to design interactive tasks for their students (Ho, ThuyAn, 2016; Le, T ThanhHoa, 2016), designing web-based materials for students of Accounting at Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry (Tran, TinNghi (b), 2014), designing computer-based translation resources for technical terms (Translation Team of Star Vietnam, 2014), understanding Business English students' preferences for actual use of website-resources for translation at UFM (Chu, QuangPhe, 2016), and using TAM to understand foreign language students' acceptance of ICT tools for studying English (Nguyen, HuuBinh, 2017; Chu, QuangPhe, 2018).

In short, although there are several studies of the application of ITC tools to teach or learn English as mentioned earlier, the research works on Economics-majored students' acceptance of ICT tools for studying English are very few; therefore, estimating their use of ICT for studying English is really urgent.

2.2 Technology Acceptance Model

Several research works have explored the factors influencing the acceptance or resistance to ICT tools, and some common factors of the frameworks are usually user attitudes, perceptions, beliefs and the actual system use (Alharbi, S. & Drew, S., 2014, p145). Davis's TAM has been widely used to explore the acceptance of ICT tools since it focuses not only on the technical aspects but on the psychological features of using ICT as well (Alharbi, S. & Drew, S., 2014; Nguyen H. , 2017; Bogart, W V.D. and Wichadee, S., 2015).

Initially developing the research model to predict computer usage acceptance, Davis (1989) explored how perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU) affected user acceptance of technology which was explained through the two dependent factors: attitude to use (ATU) and intention to use (ITU). The original framework also consisted of external variables (EV) as the moderators such as job relevance and ICT experience, which positively affected PU and PEU and moderated the framework (Davis, 1989). In this TAM, the two principal factors are PU and PEU, which are defined as the user's belief that the technology will improve their performance or help them perform their job better and as how easy the user perceives the new technology is to use respectively. Davis (1989) explained that PEU and PU are the determinants to user acceptance of technology. Then, ATU resulting in behavioral intention of whether to use or not use the technology and so is another determining factor to be explored. This model has gained support for being powerful for predicting the early adoption of new technologies that can be used in various contexts and different situations (Teo, 2009, as cited in Bogart, W V.D. and Wichadee, S., 2015).

Figure 1: TAM

(Davis, 1989)

Alharbi& Drew (2014) did a research to understand academics' behavioural intention to use the learning management system (SMS) in Saudi Arabia . They modified Davis's TAM by adding lack of LMS availability to EV and administered the questionnaire to 59 academics and found all the positive relations proven by Davis (1989). They also found that PEU positively affected ITU, which was a new relation. However, the added variables were not supported via the covariance analysis.

Bogart and Wichadee (2015) explored students' intention to use LINE¹ for academic purposes based on Davis' TAM (1989) and could predict and explain all the relationships among the TAM constructs except for the correlation between PEU and ATU and between the number of network sites as EV and ITU.

Nguyen, HuuBinh (2017) used TAM to understand students' use of ITC to study foreign languages at Danang University. He modified Davis' TAM (1989) by removing EV as the moderators. The sample consisted of 331 student subjects, and they were requested to self-report their perception of, attitude toward and intention of ICT use. After testing the hypotheses through the quantitative analysis, he found that PEU positively affected PU and PU positively affected ATT and ITU. The ATT itself affected ITU but was not affected by PEU (ibid).

Chu, QuangPhe (2018) estimated Business English-majored students' acceptance of ICT for studying ESP through Davis' TAM (1989). Since ICT tools were not provided by the university, EV was removed accordingly. The findings indicated that there existed the positive correlations among the two independent components and two dependent ones. In more detail, PEU greatly influenced PU and both of them influenced ATU; besides, although ITU was affected by ATU, PEU and PU, ATU still had the greatest impact upon ITU.

In a summary, even though there have been some researches on using Davis's TAM (1989) to estimate students' behavioral intention of using ICT, this powerful model has not been adopted to predict Economics-majored students' acceptance of tools for studying English at tertiary level. Furthermore, because the sample of this research are provided with ICT tools, consisting of connected computers, Blended Software, and wifi access, the author of this research paper

¹ An online chat application which allows users to make voice call and send messages whenever and wherever they are, (Bogart, W V.D. and Wichadee, S., 2015)

decided on all the components Davis's TAM (1989), which was composed of EV, PEU, PU, ATU and ITU.

3 Research design

3.1 Methodology

The student subjects were the undergraduates of Economics at the UFM, who were studying *General English 1* when the research was initiated. Prior to the course, they were required to buy an online account which permitted them to combine direct instructions and online self-study. After studying English via the blended approach for nine weeks, they were requested to take part in the questionnaire survey on their perception of using ICT for learning English.

Before getting the data, the author visited some selected classes, discussed the purpose of the research, and explained all the items in the questionnaire in order that the student subjects provided the reliable data for the research work. After that, they would complete the survey via the Google form and 320 students' responses were automatically recorded in Google Drive. It was highly expected that after being exposed to the blended approach to learning English, the student subjects' responses would reveal their acceptance of or resistance to ICT use in learning English.

3.2 Participants

The sample was composed of 320 first year students of Economics. The statistics show that females represent 78.1% of the student subjects. This number is quite typical for Economics majors in Vietnam where females always outnumber males.

All the student subjects owned an online account run by an app installed in a smart mobile, a tablet, a laptop computer, or a desktop computer, through which *Blended Software* provided various resources of English materials and a platform for them to experience learning such as collaborating with friends, interacting with the lecturer, studying English on their own or doing tests to measure their progress.

Concerning the student subjects' use of ICT tools, they actually adopted or possessed various kinds. In more detail, Figure 2 shows the location and retrieval tools, among which Google (89.9%), Youtube (54.1%) and Internet-based dictionaries (52.5%) are sites that they consult most to get resources for their learning English. In addition, Figure 3 indicates the use of numerous apps employed to interact with other people; more specifically, Facebook, Messenger and emails are the most used tools, representing 81.6% , 74.9% and 53.4% respectively. These apps are actually the popular for young people. Also seen in Figure 4, which presents the data on the use of hardware tools, smart phones which account for 90.3% and notebooks which make up 58.8% were the most popular tools. Finally, Figure 5 provides the information on the creation tools, among which the student subjects possess sound and video makers the most, forming 66.3%. In fact, these two tools are popular because they are very useful for students not only to study English but also to make presentations or entertain themselves.

Figure 2: Students' use of location and retrieval apps

Figure 3: Students' use of interaction tools

Figure 4: Student's use of hardware tools

In short, the students possess various ICT tools, which are used to support their learning English. These tools can range from location tools to creation ones, and they can be employed to study English either on BlendedSoftware or on the internet, or on both of them. It is notable that the advanced tools such as smart phones, sound and video makers, Facebook, Messenger, and Google are popular for students, most probably inferring that they are interested in ICT use.

Figure 5: Students' use of creation tools

3.3 Instruments

The instrument for collecting data is the questionnaire which consists of twenty one research questions representing five components of the research scale.

The first component is EV, which is made up by five variables to indicate how the student subjects' exposure to ICT affects PEU and PU. Then, PU, which is composed of four variables, is adopted to see the extent, to which the student subjects consider ICT useful for their studying English. Then, PEU is made up of five variables and is utilized to explore how easily the students use ICT tools for studying English. Next, ATU, comprising four variables, is deployed to understand their attitude toward using ICT tools for studying English, and finally, ITU, which consists of three variables, is included to see if they have the behavioral intention of using ICT tools for studying English.

The students gave their responses by clicking the five point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strong disagreement) to 5 (complete agreement). All the data was electronically recorded on the Google form for quantitative analyses and discussions later.

3.4 Hypotheses

The research scale is clearly composed of five components; hence, the hypotheses are formed to see the relationships that exist among them. More specifically, the correlations among the five factors are negatively hypothesized as the following:

H₁: PEU is not positively affected by EV.

H₂: PU is not positively affected by EV.

H₃: PU is not positively affected by PEU.

H₄: ATU is not positively affected by PEU.

H₅: ATU is not positively affected by PU.

H₆: ITU is not positively affected by PU.

H₇: ITU is not positively affected by ATU.

The above-mentioned null hypotheses, after being tested, will reveal the numeric relations among the external, independent and dependent variables.

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 2 initially indicates that 320 students' responses all are valid and statistically significant. In more detail, all of the items (except for PEU4) included in the scale are rated high since most of their means are 3.60 or higher, the level at which the student subjects agree with the given statements, and the standard deviation values range from a little higher than .92 to a little lower than 1.2, indicating that the probability distribution of each item condenses around its mean, and the student subjects are quite unanimous in the ITC use. Then, the negative skew in all items indicates that the tail is on the left side of the distribution and the kurtosis shows that the probability distribution of the data of all items (except for PEU4, PEU5 and ATU4) are higher than the normal one. In short, the descriptive statistics helps predict that the student subjects seem to have unanimous agreement with nearly all the statements in the questionnaire, providing the positive signs for their interest in using ICT for studying English.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
EV1	320	4.150	1.0954	-1.510	.136	1.754	.272
EV2	320	4.081	1.1418	-1.279	.136	.891	.272
EV3	320	3.850	1.0275	-1.091	.136	1.170	.272
EV4	320	3.750	1.0354	-.797	.136	.407	.272
EV5	320	3.713	1.0763	-.910	.136	.516	.272
PEU1	320	3.875	1.0400	-.993	.136	.698	.272
PEU2	320	3.913	.9883	-.941	.136	.812	.272
PEU3	320	3.825	.9829	-.859	.136	.736	.272
PEU4	320	3.119	1.1603	-.185	.136	-.602	.272
PEU5	320	3.369	1.0835	-.462	.136	-.170	.272
PU1	320	3.934	1.0379	-1.172	.136	1.264	.272
PU2	320	3.813	.9677	-.828	.136	.716	.272
PU3	320	3.853	.9796	-.910	.136	.947	.272
PU4	320	3.922	.8693	-.626	.136	.403	.272
ATU1	320	3.947	.9796	-1.121	.136	1.394	.272
ATU2	320	3.934	1.0134	-1.123	.136	1.173	.272

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
ATU3	320	3.891	.9908	-.985	.136	1.007	.272
ATU4	320	3.863	1.0139	-.665	.136	-.104	.272
ITU1	320	3.863	.9921	-.981	.136	1.039	.272
ITU2	320	4.006	.9268	-.916	.136	.885	.272
ITU3	320	3.919	.9500	-.830	.136	.648	.272
Valid N (listwise)	320						

Prior to the exploratory factor analysis, the reliability of the data needs to be assessed via the Cronbach Alpha. In the light of statistics, all the components of the research model are supposed to have the internal consistency reliability when Cronbach Alpha values reach .70 or higher. As can be seen in Table 4, the reliability of each component and the overall reliability are quite high, meaning that the data is good enough for further analyses.

Table 3: Data reliability

Components	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha
EV	5	.884
PEU	5	.834
PU	4	.859
ATU	4	.863
ITU	3	.873
Overall reliability	21	.950

(Cronbach Alpha)

After the reliability of the data is assessed and is proven to be statistically significant, the principal component analysis is performed to locate the variables. Table 5 indicates that all of the 21 variables are retained as their factor loadings reach above the statistical significance of .50, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy tops at .919 and Bartlett's test of sphericity gets the significant value of below .05. On the whole, all of these indexes indicate that the research model is ready for further analyses.

The initial eigenvalue of the first three independent factors is 1.196 (>1) and the accumulative extraction sum of squared loads is 65.879%, meaning that there exist three factors in the research scale, plus ITU. Also can be seen from Table 4, through the rotation method of Varimax with Kaiser normalization, the five original factors of the research model are regrouped down to four and some variables some are mixed up within the research model. Therefore, the research model now contains EV (EV1, EV2, EV3, EV4, EV5); PEU (PEU1, PEU2, PEU3, PEU4, PEU5,

PEU6←ATU4); BAU (BAU1←PU1, BAU2←PU2, BAU3←PU3, BAU4←PU4, BAU5←ATU1, BAU6←ATU2, BAU7←ATU3) and ITU(ITU1, ITU2, ITU3), among which BAU, standing for the behavioral attitude to use, is defined as the like for using ICTtools because of their usefulness.

Table 4: Exploratory factor analysis

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
ATU2	.829			
ATU3	.810			
PU2	.793			
ATU1	.764			
PU1	.692			
PU3	.692			
PU4	.638			
EV3		.845		
EV4		.807		
EV2		.755		
EV5		.732		
EV1		.641		
PEU4			.816	
PEU5			.571	
PEU2			.565	
PEU1			.529	
PEU3			.513	
ATU4			.500	
ITU2				.907
ITU3				.894
ITU1				.879

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Table 5 shows the correlations existing among the components of the new model. All the constructs bear the positive correlations, and the significant index falls far below .05, meaning that the statistical significance is obtained. In other words, the table helps explain the positive relations existing among the components of the research model, and when there is a change in one construct, it will lead to the change of the others that follow in the model.

Table 5: Correlations

		EV	PEU	BAU	ITU
EV	Pearson Correlation	1	.644**	.612**	.527**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	320	320	320	320
PEU	Pearson Correlation	.644**	1	.717**	.695**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	320	320	320	320
BAU	Pearson Correlation	.612**	.717**	1	.794**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	320	320	320	320
ITU	Pearson Correlation	.527**	.695**	.794**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	320	320	320	320

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5 also helps test the null hypotheses stated in Section 3.4 to confirm the influence of one factor on another/ others. Based on the statistical figure of this table, only H₁ is proven, meaning that EV positively affects PEU, while the others are not because PEU and ATU are grouped as BAU. Because all the correlations are positive, the increase of this factor will naturally result in that of the factor that follows in the research model.

To further explore the correlation and the extent, to which one factor influences the others, the structural equations model with the weight path is employed. In Figure 6, the correlation can be explained more clearly. EV influences both PEU and BAU, in which it affects the former one more with the regression weight of .82. Besides, although PEU has some impact on BAU and ITU, the bigger weight path exists between it and BAU. Finally, though impacted by both PEU and BAU, ITU is affected by the latter more (.68).

On the whole, Figure 6 helps forecast Economics-majored students' acceptance of resistance to ICT use for learning English. The structural equations model indicates that the students' experience with ICT tools is the major factor helping them feel that the ICT tools are easy to use. Both their experiences and perceived ease of use are the determinants to the fact that they like ICT tools and perceive that the ICT tools are useful for them in studying English. Then, when they like ICT tools and find them helpful, this will result in their actual use of ICT.

Figure 6: Students' acceptance of ICT

4.3 Findings

The descriptive analysis in Table 4 indicates that college students are interested in adopting ICT tools for learning English and current possess various tools, which can make their learning fruitful.

The confirmatory factor analysis via Figure 2 shows that if expected to use more ICT tools, students should perceive their usefulness and have a positive attitude towards ICT use beforehand. Then, if wanting them to enhance the behavioral attitude towards ICT, they should feel that ICT is easy to use and should be given the chance of exposure to ICT use. Finally, if helping students feel that ICT tools are easy to use, lecturers and/or HEIs should let their students experience the use of these tools.

The findings of this research paper are quite different from the previous studies done by Chu, QuangPhe (2018), Nguyen, HuuBinh's (2017), Bogart and Wichadee's (2015), and Alharbi & Drew's (2014). The difference of the findings must be tracked to the approach indeed. In this research, the student subjects have much experiences with Blended Software to study English, and they might have limited ICT tools to this software. Due to its user-friendly feature, this leads to the fact that EV and PEU influence BAU relatively equally. Besides, the student subjects hardly make large differences between PEU and ITU, causing the fact that the two components are grouped to make a combined one.

To summarize, the research has successfully explained the positive correlations among the four factors in the diagram and affirmed the impact of one factor on the other or others.

5 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The paper has been successful in applying Davis's TAM (1989) to explaining the factors that affect college students' behavioral intention of using ICT tools for studying English. Through the descriptive statistics, the exploratory factor analysis, the correlative statistics, and the structural equations model, the research model proves to be fit and clearly locates the components and their positive correlations among them. These factors indeed can help lecturers of English estimate their students' acceptance of ICT tools, and they know what they should do if they want to increase their college students' use of ICT in studying English.

5.2 Implications

Based on the findings of the research, the author would recommend some implications for HEIs, lecturers of English and students who are studying English as below.

Since EV plays quite crucial a role in helping students feel it easy and useful to use ICT tools; thus, they should be given an opportunity to use it. This means that HEIs should provide various ICT tools to support their students' learning of English and make sure that these tools are connected to the Internet to maximize their opportunity of learning English. Besides the facilities equipped by HEIs, students themselves should adopt their own devices for studying as long as they benefit them in terms of resources and internet access.

Students should be aware of the usefulness and ease of use in order that they can change their attitude towards ICT use for learning English; hence, the HEIs should provide college students with tools that are user-friendly and the tools should have certain features to benefit their learning.

When wanting to increase college students' use of ICT tools for learning English, lecturers should help students change their attitude first. Then, lecturers of English should master the use of ICT tools and then train their students to guarantee that they know how to use ICT tools beneficially for their learning English. When they feel like using ICT tools for studying English, they will have the intention of adopting these tools to support their learning.

In general, taking into account of certain situations helps locate which factors of the diagram in Figure 6 lecturers and/or students should stimulate in order that students accept ICT use for studying English. While ICT tools make an indispensable part teaching and learning English nowadays, the research can help explain whether students accept the use of ICT tools for learning English and how lecturers can facilitate the use of these tools.

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QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

PART 1. BACKGROUND QUESTIONS

1. Gender: Male or Female

2. Indicate which ICT tools you have for learning English

desktop computer smart phone tablet

CD/VCD player e-dictionary

others: _____

3. Indicate which ICTsubtools you have for learning English

Google Wikipedia websites

Youtube Internet dictionary e-learning pages

others: _____

4. Indicate which ICT tools you have for learning English

Word processing software (words, excel...)

Presentation software (powerpoint, mindmap...)

audio-visual tools (video maker, recorder...)

others: _____

5. Indicate which ICT tools you have for learning English

email Messenger Instagram

Facebook Lines Skype

Zalo Viber

others: _____

PART 2: STUDY QUESTIONS

Codes	Variables					
EV1	I have ICT tools.	1	2	3	4	5
EV2	I use ICT tools every day.	1	2	3	4	5
EV3	I use ICT tools for learning needs.	1	2	3	4	5
EV4	I use ICT for learning English.	1	2	3	4	5
EV5	The college creates good conditions for using ICT for learning.	1	2	3	4	5
PEU1	I feel that using ICT would be easy for me.	1	2	3	4	5
PEU2	I feel that my interaction with ICT would be clear and understandable.	1	2	3	4	5
PEU3	It would be easy for me to use ICT to do what I want to do.	1	2	3	4	5
PEU4	Using ICT does not require any special skills.	1	2	3	4	5
PEU5	Learning to use ICT to study English would be easy for me	1	2	3	4	5
PU1	I feel that using ICT would help me study English better.	1	2	3	4	5
PU2	I feel that using ICT would increase my performance.	1	2	3	4	5
PU3	I feel that using ICT would enable me to handle bigger workload.	1	2	3	4	5
PU4	I feel that using ICT would be an effective tool for me to study English.	1	2	3	4	5
ATU1	It is a good idea to use ICT to study English.	1	2	3	4	5
ATU2	ICT makes studying more interesting.	1	2	3	4	5
ATU3	Studying English with ICT is really interesting.	1	2	3	4	5
ATU4	I like using ICT tools to study.	1	2	3	4	5
ITU1	I expect to experience academic courses via the use of ICT tools.	1	2	3	4	5
ITU2	In the future, I will use ICT in studying.	1	2	3	4	5
ITU3	I plan to use ICT in studying English.	1	2	3	4	5

Please, mark the number below to show your responses: 1 (strong disagreement), 2 (disagreement), 3 (neutrality), 4 (agree) and 5 (completely agreement)

THE END